

ANALYSIS OF CONFLICT AND NATIONAL INTERESTS OF LEBANON AND ISRAEL WITH THE THEORY OF CONSTRUCTIVISM

ANALISIS KONFLIK DAN KEPENTINGAN NASIONAL LEBANON DAN ISRAEL DENGAN TEORI KONTRUKTIVISME

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ABSTRACT

There have been many agreements from both parties such as resolutions from the United Nations and maritime demarcations mediated by the United States. Israel and Lebanon have a complex relationship, where it is not uncommon for the two countries to be in conflict. The conflict between Lebanon and Israel began when the PLO (Palestine Liberation Organization) moved to the country of Lebanon, this prompted Israel to target an attack on Beirut and also launch an operation to eradicate the PLO. Based on the research conducted, it can be said that the conflict between Lebanon and Israel is an old story caused by regional and religious issues. The conflict between the two countries was never fully resolved and formal peace was established. However, between the existing conflicts, the two countries did not take action against each other even though they were still in a cold state. This act of mutual attack sparked an increasingly heated conflict, especially since it has reached each other's national boundaries. Actually, there have been no results that are significant enough to explain the separation between the two countries, but the efforts that have been made are sufficient to explain how the solution to the war is.

ABSTRAK

Telah banyak perjanjian dari kedua belah pihak seperti resolusi dari PBB dan demarkasi maritim yang dimediasi Amerika Serikat, Israel dan Lebanon memiliki hubungan kompleks, dimana tidak jarang kedua negara tersebut berkonflik. Konflik antara Lebanon dan Israel diawali pada saat itu PLO (Palestine Liberation Organization) berpindah ke negara Lebanon, hal tersebut membuat Israel untuk menargetkan serangan ke Beirut dan juga melancarkan operasi untuk memberantas PLO. Berdasarkan penelitian yang dilakukan, dapat dikatakan bahwa Konflik antara Lebanon dan Israel merupakan kisah lama yang dikarenakan persoalan wilayah dan agama. Konflik antara kedua negara ini tidak pernah benar-benar selesai dan melakukan perdamaian resmi. Namun, diantara konflik yang ada kedua negara ini sempat tidak melakukan aksi saling serang meski tetap dalam keadaan dingin. Aksi saling serang ini memicu konflik yang semakin memanas apalagi sudah mencapai batas negara satu sama lain. Sebenarnya belum ada hasil yang cukup signifikan untuk menjelaskan pelebaran antara kedua negara ini, namun upaya yang dilakukan cukup untuk menjelaskan bagaimana solusi atas perang tersebut.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Middle East is a region that is politically and culturally part of the continent of Asia, or Africa-Eurasia. This region has a strategic geographical location for global economic and defense strategy. In addition, the Middle East also has the largest natural resources in the form of oil and natural gas, has many tribes and historical sources from several religions.

However, this area is considered as an unstable, conflictual area to the point where there are many

wars. Differences in ethnicity, religion, and socio-economic disparities are the causes of this region being an area that is prone to inter-religious and ethnic conflicts and power struggles between certain ethnic groups. Not to mention the added element of natural wealth such as petroleum which is the main factor in the division of the country. One example is the Israel and Lebanon War.

Israel is bordered on the west by the Suez Canal and Egypt, on the south by Egypt, on the east by Jordan

and on the north by Lebanon. Israel also has an area of 20,770 square Km. Meanwhile, the topography of Lebanon is the area is hilly with beaches extending along the Mediterranean Sea from the north bordering Syria to the south bordering Israel. Lebanon has an area of 10,452 square kilometers.

While Israel has been a state for 75 years, the majority of Israelis are Jewish. 41% of the world's Jewish population lives in Israel. Judaism is the majority religion in Israel. Based on identification in 2018, the percentage of religions in Israel is Judaism (74.3%), followed by Muslims (17.8%), Christians (1.9%), Druze (1.6%) and several other religions (4.4%) (Cita Najma Zenitha, 2023). Israel has been at war with Palestine since 1948, when Israel itself became a newly independent state. One of the causes was the struggle for the Gaza territory in 1967. (CNN Indonesia, 2021).

Meanwhile, Lebanese people have various religions, it is estimated that there are 54% Muslim (27% Shia, 27% Sunni), 40.5% Christian (including 21% Maronite Catholics, 8% Greek Orthodox, 5% Melkite Catholics, 1% Protestantism in Lebanon, 5.5% other Christians), Druze 5.6%, and a very small number of Jews, Baha'is, Buddhists, Hindus, and Mormons (CIA World Factbook, 2019). In fact, in Lebanon there is Hezbollah, a political and paramilitary organization of Shia Islamic groups which was founded on June 6, 1982 as a response to the Israeli invasion of Lebanon.

Because of this, Lebanon has become a destination country for Palestinian refugees who seek protection. What's more, at that time the PLO (Palestine Liberation Organization) which was established in Jordan on June 2, 1964 was expelled from the country because Jordan was exposed to threats from the Israeli military. The PLO eventually moved and developed in Lebanon, this became the target of Israel to launch an attack on Beirut and Israel also launched an operation to eradicate the PLO. From this event, new conflicts began to emerge between Lebanon and Israel.

Like the conflict that occurred in 1993, Israel finally withdrew unconditionally. In 2006 there was also a major conflict between the two countries involving Hezbollah and the Israeli army which forced the United Nations to intervene and make a resolution to resolve the conflict. Until 2022, countries are still frequently in disputes, for example disputes over sea border areas which are areas of dispute for both parties. However, Lebanon and Israel were able to

rescind the maritime demarcation (sea boundary) agreement mediated by the United States on October 27, 2022. With this agreement, offshore energy exploration that is profitable for the two neighboring countries, can be opened and is expected to make the relationship between the two is good without any conflict.

Unfortunately, on April 7, 2023 the Israeli military announced an attack on Lebanese territory after launching an attack on Gaza, Palestine. This made the situation in the region even more tense. The Israeli army announced that they carried out an attack in Lebanon in the early hours of the morning local time.

The interesting thing is, even though there have been many agreements from both parties such as resolutions from the United Nations and maritime demarcations mediated by the United States, the two countries are still often in dispute. Apart from that, the beginning of this dispute was from Lebanon which trying to help Palestinian refugees.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Theoretical Framework

The theory used is constructivist theory where relations between countries will be influenced by historical factors from the country itself. In addition, the similarity of fate and background is also a factor. Usually countries will feel that other countries are rivals or friends based on this. Later, the relationship between the two countries will reflect what was decided according to constructivism theory. To find out this, it takes a very long time by relying on the historical factors of the country concerned.

According to the German thinker, Nicolas Onuf in his book entitled *World of Our Making* which states that constructivism thinking is influenced by The Linguistic Turn. There are three things, including linguistic symbols which are used as a communication medium that will form something that is perceived. Then, words or Speech Act which means policies or rules that can affect humans. Furthermore, as a medium that can control and distribute information from a subject. Onuf has also popularized constructivism as a perspective in International Relation.

The current conflict between Israel and Lebanon is basically a historical factor which has a background of a series of disputes between the two countries

concerned. Bearing in mind, Lebanon is a country that has good relations with Israel's enemy, namely Palestine, so Israel will continue to view Lebanon as its rival country. Israel does not allow Lebanon not to attack its state-claimed gas assets. Israel emphatically stated this and would declare war if Lebanon did. According to Israel, the area is its country's Exclusive Economic Zone.

Basically, this is a territorial dispute conflict between Lebanon and Israel in which Lebanon prohibits Israel from drilling in the area. And Israel also does not want Lebanon to interfere with its country's internal affairs concerning gas fields. This conflict grew after Israel launched an attack on the Gaza strip, this also received a response from the United Nations (UN). UN troops while in Lebanon said that both the Lebanese and Israeli sides must stop their actions along the blue line (Blue Line). The blue line is the demarcation line between Lebanon and Israel.

The actions of the two continued to attack each other where Israel launched its attacks by air towards Lebanon after attacking the Gaza Strip on Friday, April 7, 2023. Israel's confession was to attack targets belonging to the Palestinian resistance, namely Hamas, in South Lebanon. The Israeli armed forces said that Lebanon should take full responsibility for all fire aimed at Israel from Lebanese territory.

B. Concept of National Interest

The national interest is a goal and ambition of the country in various aspects including the economic, military and cultural fields (Bainus and Rachman 2018). National interests have a fairly close relationship with the actualization of the strength or power possessed by a country to achieve its goals. In the classical sense, the use of power in the context of achieving national interests is generally correlated with a destructive policy orientation. The destructive use of power is referred to as hard power. (Nye, 1990).

When national interests aim to pursue power and power is used as an instrument to achieve national interests, the consequences in an international system that is perceived as anarchy, except for power itself is competition, the emergence of a balance of power such as conflict.

C. Concept of Conflict

Etymologically, "conflict" comes from the Latin "con" which means together and "fligere" which means collision. Thus "conflict" in social life means a clash of interests, desires, opinions, etc. involving two or more parties. In addition, this anthropological understanding of conflict does not stand alone, but together with the notion of conflict according to other aspects, all of which take part in creating social conflict in human collective life (Chang, 2001).

Described from an anthropological sense, in the International Encyclopaedia of The Social Sciences Vol. 3 (pages 236-241) explains that the conflict arises as a result of competition between at least two parties; where each party can be an individual, family, kinship group, a community, or maybe a layer of social class supporting a particular ideology, a political organization, an ethnic group, or a follower of a particular religion (Nader, t.t.). However, the conflict has experienced development, involving between countries, between tribes within the same country, to feuds between the government and community groups. It is the conflict that occurs within a country or between countries that then causes war (Muhammadiyah University of Yogyakarta, 2015).

III. DISCUSSION

A. History of the Conflict between Israel and Lebanon

Initially, Lebanon became the destination country for Palestinian refugees who asked for protection after Israel became independent on Palestinian land, this became the target of Israel to launch an attack on Beirut and Israel also launched an operation to eradicate the PLO (Palestine Liberation Organization) which was founded in Jordan on June 2, 1964 but then moved and developed in Lebanon after the expulsion of the PLO from Jordan by the Jordanian government itself due to the threat of an Israeli military attack.

Israel continues to invade Lebanon without stopping if the Palestinian people and the PLO are still under the protection of the Lebanese Government and Hezbollah. However, this did not deter Lebanese steps against Israel. South Lebanon is the border area between Lebanon and Israel which is the headquarters of Palestinian and Hezbollah militias. The existence of the Lebanese militia headquarters made Israel uncomfortable so that it launched an attack.

In 1993, Israel launched "Operation Accountability" which consisted of one week of air, artillery, and sea attacks, followed by "Operation Grape of Wrath" in 1996, a 17-day military action. The fighting between Israel and Hezbollah has weakened Israel's resolve and led to the collapse of the militias. In 2000 the Israeli army withdrew unconditionally from Lebanon towards the border area that had been designated directly by the United Nations.

After its invasion of Lebanon, in 2006 Israel was involved in a major war between the Lebanese Hezbollah. Hizbullah is by definition defined as the Party of Allah/Party of God. Hezbollah is a Political and Paramilitary organization of the Shia Islamic group which was founded on June 6, 1982 in Lebanon as a response to the Israeli invasion of Lebanon. After 6 years, Israel and Lebanon again experienced conflict. A series of military actions and ongoing clashes in Israel and Lebanon involving the armed wing of Hezbollah and the Israel Defense Forces. Starting on July 12, 2006, when Hezbollah attacked the city of Shlomi in Northern Israel with Katyusha missiles, then Hezbollah troops infiltrated Israeli territory. In the attack, three Israeli troops were killed, two were injured, and two were kidnapped. This act of arrest is in line with Hezbollah's plan which is called Operation Truthful Promise or an honest promise. The aim of the Truthful Promise operation is to free the captives kidnapped by Israel by means of a prisoner exchange.

This event then continued with Hezbollah's attack on Israeli territory which resulted in eight Israeli soldiers being killed and injuring more than 20 people. Israel then retaliated with Operation Change of Direction 11. The counteroffensive included rocket fire aimed at Lebanon and bombardments by the Israeli Air Force (IAF), an Air and Naval blockade and several minor incursions into southern Lebanon by IDF ground troops.

Israel attacked Lebanon using the excuse of the capture of two Israeli soldiers by Hezbollah in a cross-border attack. Hezbollah plans to use these captives to carry out a prisoner exchange to free Lebanese and Palestinians held by Israel. This major Israeli attack caught Hezbollah by surprise, which had previously expected Israel to retaliate with a commando operation to kidnap Hezbollah members, as Israel had long been preparing for this attack with US permission. Hezbollah responded Back by

launching rockets into northern Israel. Israeli Prime Minister Ehud Olmert said the attacks would stop if Hezbollah released the two Israeli soldiers. Finally, Israel's military aggression against Lebanon for 34 days stopped. On August 12, 2006, the United Nations Security Council passed (Resolution 1701) and it was adopted on August 14, 2006. After (Resolution 1701) was passed, Israel began to stop its military attacks and withdrew its troops from the Lebanese territory. In addition, the captives of the two Israeli soldiers were also released unconditionally. Resolution 1701 reinforced UN Security Council resolution 1559, which stated that all militias outside the official Lebanese military, including Hezbollah, must be disarmed.

B. Rocket Attack Israel and Lebanon Conflict

The Israeli military said that 34 rockets were fired from Lebanese territory and 25 of them were intercepted by the Israeli air defense system, Iron Dome. The Israeli military stated that five rockets landed on Israeli territory. In retaliation, Friday, April 7, 2023, the Israeli military struck a number of targets in southern Lebanon and Gaza City. The Israeli military said the target of their attack was several infrastructures belonging to the Hamas group in southern Lebanon. Lebanese television station, Al Mayadeen said an explosion was heard in the city of Tyre, a port city in the south of the country.

The Israeli attack on Lebanese territory was questioned by the interim prime minister of Lebanon, Najib Mikati. He said Lebanon, assisted by UN peacekeepers, was investigating the matter and trying to find the perpetrators of the rocket shooting. Mikati said his government firmly rejects military escalation and the use of its territory to carry out actions that threaten stability.

So far, no group in Lebanon has claimed responsibility for the rocket attacks on Israeli territory. Hezbollah, which condemned the Israeli security forces' raid on the Al Aqsa Mosque compound, did not respond to requests for comment on the rocket attack. Both Israel and Hezbollah have avoided all-out conflict since a 34-day war in 2006 that ended in a draw.

Rocket attacks from Israel to Lebanon and Gaza following the attack by Israeli security forces on the Al Aqsa Mosque complex are feared to expand and result in a situation that cannot be controlled. The UN

special coordinator for the Middle East peace process, Tor Wennesland, urged the leaders of the parties to refrain from actions that are counterproductive to the peace process. The attack on Lebanon was preceded by diplomatic talks between the governments in Beirut and West Jerusalem. According to the UN peacekeeping mission, UNIFIL, Israel and Lebanon affirm that they do not want an escalation of war, even though Israel demands its right to defend itself.

The Lebanese Prime Minister, Najib Mikati, has since rejected "escalation" following an attack on Israel from its territory. On Friday, the Lebanese military announced it had disarmed its "ready-to-fire rocket launcher mode" in the border area with Israel. The Shia militant group, Hezbollah, also said it was not behind the attack on Israel. However, they are on alert and will support "all efforts" by Palestinian groups to resist the Israeli occupation. The threat was previously made by Hamas leader Ismaily Haniyeh, who arrived in Lebanon the day before the Israeli attack. He told media he would not "sit down" and remain silent" in the face of Israeli "aggression" at al-Aqsa. The UN Secretary General, Antonio Guterres, who previously criticized the Israeli occupation police raid on al-Aqsa Mosque, now urges all parties to exercise restraint as much as possible.

C. National Interest Israel and Lebanon

Lebanon has the political organization Hezbollah whose ideology is Shia Islam. Hezbollah was formed by the Lebanese government to deal with the impact of the Israeli invasion on Lebanese territory because Lebanon is a refuge for Palestinians. Currently, the United Nations recognizes that there are more than 5.9 million Palestinian refugees, many of whom live in makeshift refugee camps in Jordan, Gaza, the West Bank, Syria and Lebanon (Paula Rosas, 2023)

In addition, Hezbollah also aims to recapture the Lebanese territories which were occupied and controlled by Israel and end the Zionist Israeli occupation of the territories of the State of Lebanon because part of the Lebanese territory has been taken by Israel to become the Greater Israel state (Ridwan Sahidin, 2014).

Israel also has national interests. The country annexed Lebanon not without reason. Since the beginning the Israeli state wanted Southern Lebanon, the area contained the Litani, Hasbani and Wazzani Rivers which were the sources of water and the soil around

the river flow was very fertile. With the aim, to be able to flow water to residential areas in the northern part of Israel.

Various actions were carried out by the Israeli military, patrolling the area and encroaching on the territory of the Lebanese state. Israel also invaded Lebanon because it wanted to attack Palestinian refugees who were in Lebanese makeshift camps. Israel hates the existence of Palestine because it also wants to seize the territory because Palestine is so integral to the history, geography and nature of the landscape it claims as its own.

IV. CONCLUSION

The conflict between Lebanon and Israel is an old story caused by territorial and religious issues. The dispute between the two has sparked many attacks that have taken place in the country concerned and in the surrounding region. Lebanon has become a destination country for Palestinian refugees seeking protection. At that time, the PLO (Palestine Liberation Organization) which was established in Jordan on June 2, 1964 was expelled from the country because Jordan was under threats from the Israeli military. The PLO finally moved and developed in Lebanon, this of course made Lebanon. Became the target of Israel to launch its attack on Beirut and Israel also launched operations to eradicate the PLO.

In 1993, Israel launched "Operation Accountability" which involved air, artillery and sea attacks for one week. This was followed by "Operation Grape of Wrath" in 1996, a 17-day military action. The fighting between Israel and Hezbollah has weakened Israel's resolve and led to the collapse of the militia. In 2000, the Israeli army withdrew unconditionally from Lebanon towards the border area that had been directly designated by the United Nations. In 2006, there was a major conflict between the two countries involving Hezbollah and the Israeli army, which made the United Nations step in and make a resolution to resolve the conflict. Israel was involved in a major war between the Lebanese Hezbollah and the Israeli military.

After 6 years, Israel and Lebanon again experienced conflict. A series of military actions and ongoing clashes in Israel and Lebanon involving the armed wing of Hezbollah and the Israel Defense Forces. It started on July 12, 2006, when Hezbollah attacked the Israeli city of Shlomi. North with Katshuya Missiles,

then Hezbollah troops infiltrated Israeli territory. This event continued with Hezbollah's attack on Israeli territory which resulted in eight Israeli soldiers being killed and injuring more than 20 people. Israel then retaliated with Operation Just Reward, which was renamed Operation Change of Direction 11. The counteroffensive included rocket fire aimed at Lebanon and bombardments by the Israeli Air Force (IAF), an Air and Naval blockade and several minor incursions into southern Lebanon by IDF ground troops.

After that, Israel and Lebanon returned to conflict in 2023, to be precise on April 7, 2023 where Israel carried out a military aggression on the Al-Aqsa Mosque area which received a serious response from Palestinians including Hamas. Ismail Haniyeh as the leader of Hamas said that this time in response to Israel's actions, the Palestinians will not remain silent, this statement was made in Beirut, Lebanon. Then he met a number of Palestinian resistance groups there. After this happened, Israel received an attack in which dozens of rockets thought to have come from Lebanon invaded the Israeli Military Aggression area at the Al-Aqsa Mosque. The Israeli military said that 34 rockets were fired from Lebanese territory and 25 of them were intercepted by the Israeli air defense system, Iron Dome.

Israel carried out a counterattack aimed at the Lebanese area on June 7, 2023. Then Israeli attacks took place in several coastal areas controlled by the Palestinian militant group, Hamas. Several rockets were then fired from Gaza towards Israel in response to the airstrikes. Israel said an IDF drone had attacked a heavy machine gun in northern Gaza that was used to fire shells at IDF jets and Israeli territory. Hours before the IDF attack on Gaza, Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu warned Israel would "hit our enemies and they will pay the price for every act of aggression." The attack on each other occurred when the public was angry over the Israeli police raid on the Al-Aqsa Mosque.

Prime Minister Najib Mikati said that the violations committed by Israel by carrying out the aggression on the Al-Aqsa Mosque would sacrifice the entire region. UNIFIL, the UN peacekeeping mission in Lebanon, both sides were not seeking war but said the situation was at risk of escalation and urged all sides to stop their actions. Later the Arab League convened an emergency meeting after which it condemned the

attack and said it endangered regional stability. Meanwhile, the United Arab Emirates (UAE) and China asked the 15-member UN Security Council to discuss the situation in Palestine behind closed doors.

In fact, the conflict between the two countries was never really resolved and official peace was made. However, between the existing conflicts, the two countries did not take action against each other even though they were still in a cold state. This act of mutual attack sparked an increasingly heated conflict, especially since it has reached each other's national boundaries. Actually, there have been no results that are significant enough to explain the separation between the two countries, but the efforts that have been made are sufficient to explain how the solution to the war is. This research is based on Constructivism theory which will continue to build opinions as well as new facts related to the conflict between Israel and Lebanon.

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